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Research Article

**DEVELOPMENT OF CIPROFLOXACIN HYDROCHLORIDE
LOADED *IN-SITU* GEL FOR THE TREATMENT OF
PERIODONTITIS: *IN-VITRO* DRUG RELEASE STUDY AND
ANTI-BACTERIAL ACTIVITY**Praveen Sivadasu*, Boppudi Bindu Sri, Gorre Asha, Bhukya Chandana, Abdul Safiya
Naseema, Mamillapalli Sneha Latha, Padmalatha KVijaya Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences for Women, Enikepadu, Vijayawada-521 108
Krishna district Andhra Pradesh, India.

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Abstract:

Background and Aim: Periodontitis is one of the widest spread oral diseases. Medicated *in-situ* gels of Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride (CH) for an extended period of retention in the infected cavity were prepared for improved local action for the treatment of periodontitis. **Methods:** Medicated formulations were prepared using ion-sensitive (badam gum) and pH-sensitive (carbopol 934P) polymers. The central composite design was employed and prepared batches were characterized by FTIR, pH, syringeability, drug content, clarity, gelation temperature, gelling time, *in-vitro* gelling capacity, *in-vitro* diffusion study. **Results:** Gelation temperature, (*in-vitro*) gelling time and the nature of gel formed in simulated saliva showed polymeric concentration dependency. The diffusion study of optimized *in-situ* gel had been performed which showed augmented arrival of medication from 7-10 hours and the discharge was dependent on polymer utilized. *In vitro* anti-microbial study was carried out by utilizing *E.coli* and *S.aureus* and the results suggested that formulated *in situ* gel have better anti-microbial activity when compared with pure CH. **Conclusion:** The formulated CH loaded *in situ* gel can be used as an alternative approach to treat periodontitis.

Keywords: Periodontitis; *In situ* gel; Sustained drug delivery; Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride; Polymers; Central composite design.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Sivadasu Praveen,**

Asst. Professor,

Dept. of Pharmaceutics,

Vijaya Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences for Women

Enikepadu-521108, Vijayawada, Andhra Pradesh, India

E-mail address: praveen.sivadasu399@gmail.com

Tel.: +91 9739967534

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Periodontitis (PDT) disease was known to mankind from ancient times. Physicians and researchers have established different forms of this disease, clinical symptoms, and the rate at which disease progression happens [1-3]. Chronic periodontitis is termed as a progressive disease where gingival periodontal ligament and alveolar bone will be affected and as a result of this infection, there will be a change in tooth structure leading to alveolar bone resorption [4-6].

Periodontitis can be diagnosed by understanding the anatomy of healthy gums. A healthy gum will be in pink colour stippled firmly to the underlying tissue, scalloped at cemento-enamel junction with a gingival crevice of 1-3 mm without any bleeding and this attached gingiva extends from gingival groove to mucogingival junction by tightly binding to the underlying bone and resists any kind of injury [7]. Further, any kind of deviations from this condition will lead to either gingivitis or periodontitis. Gingivitis is considered as an acute and a reversible condition where inflammation is restricted to only marginal and surrounding connective tissue without any loss of attachment. Whereas, periodontitis is considered as a chronic and irreversible condition which occurs when the inflammation reaches the periodontal ligament and alveolar bone [8, 9].

The pocket formation between tooth surface and gingiva occurs due to apical displacement of the epithelium at the junctions which can be termed as a primary indicator for periodontitis. However, it is known that not all cases of gingivitis will lead to periodontitis [10]. Conventional treatments options are used to reduce the bacterial flora, lessen inflammation and to discontinue bone desorption. Further, these conventional therapies possess certain disadvantages like insufficient drug concentration at target site, recurrent chances of bacterial resistance, incapability to provide sustained drug release effect and access deeper areas of periodontal pocket [11].

In recent times researchers paying a lot of attention in delivering the drugs locally for longer periods by using bio-adhesive polymers. Exploration of bio-adhesive drug delivery is considered as a key step in the treatment of periodontal diseases [12]. Further, there is a need for a novel drug delivery system which can be controlled more quickly and easily positioned in a periodontal pocket for the release of loaded drug for a longer duration [13]. Therefore, the controlled drug delivery approach of in-situ gel is used to deliver ciprofloxacin hydrochloride (CH) through the subgingival route. *In situ* gels can be used to deliver the loaded drug in a controlled manner by accessing the target site

directly with improved patient compliance and reduced adverse effects [14].

CH is a synthetic fluoroquinolone derivative. It is quickly active against bacteria like *Peptostreptococcus* species, *Clostridium difficile*, the *Clostridium* species, *Bacteroids* species, *Bacteroids fragilis*, *Prevotella* species, *Porphyromonas* species, *Fusobacterium* species, *Actinomycetes*, *Propionibacterium* species, and the *Eubacterium* species. Ciprofloxacin shows its action by hindering the synthesis of DNA in bacteria [15].

In this current work, an attempt has been made to formulate an in-situ gel loaded with CH using natural bioadhesive polymer like badam gum which may help in increasing patient compliance and thereby act as an alternative approach to treat periodontitis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials

Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride was obtained as a gift sample from Alembic Pharmaceuticals Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India. While, Badam gum was purchased from Thanjai orgofarms Pvt. Ltd, Chennai, India. Further Carbopol 934p was purchased from Sigma Aldrich Chemicals Pvt. Ltd., Bangalore, India.

Methods

Compatibility studies

FT-IR analysis

The Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectra of CH, badam gum, carbopol 934P, and physical mixture were recorded using the Shimadzu8400S spectrometer (Tokyo, Japan) to evaluate the compatibility between the selected drugs and polymers. A physical mixture was prepared by employing potassium bromide pellet method. Evaluation of compatibility was done by observing any peak shifts, appearance or disappearance of peaks in pure drug, total lipids and their physical mixture [16].

Preparation of CH loaded *in-situ* gel [17]

Dry badam gum powder was dispersed in 90 ml of distilled water maintained at 95°C and stirred for 20 min using a magnetic stirrer to facilitate hydration of badam gum. The required amount of disodium edetate was added to the badam gum solution with continuous stirring at 95°C. The solution was allowed to cool to room temperature. The required amount of CH was added to the badam gum solution with continuous stirring until the entire drug was dissolved. The required amount of carbopol 934P was added with continuous mild stirring for 5 min. The formulations containing partially dissolved carbopol 934P were stored in the refrigerator until the entire polymer was completely

dissolved (~48 hrs). The final volume was adjusted to 100 ml with distilled, deionized water.

Experimental design

To demonstrate the response surface model by attaining a different combination of values Design expert software (Version 12, Stat-Ease Inc., and Minneapolis, U.S.A.) was employed. Central composite design (CCD) is used to form a second-order quadratic equation without using a complete three-level factorial experiment. A 2 factor, 2 level central composite design was used to design the optimized procedure to formulate the desired *in-situ* gel. Wherein the selected independent variables are badam gum and carbopol 934P, while selected dependent variables were gelation temperature, gelling time and time required to release 90% of the drug in hrs. This leads to a process of optimization with a small experimental design (13 runs). The dependent and independent variables used in the design are depicted in the following Table 1.

Table 1: Details of Central composite design for CH loaded *in-situ* gel.

Independent variables	Dependent variables
A: Badam gum B: Carbopol 934P	R1: Gelation temperature (°C) R2: Gelling time (sec) R3: Time required to release 90% of drug (hrs)

Optimization of CH loaded *in-situ* gel

Desirability function in design expert software was used to obtain the optimized *in-situ* gel. Wherein this desirability function estimates the effect of each factor at each level on the desired response and predicts the maximum desirability which in turn identifies the optimized points. The optimized points were identified based on 5 points i.e. within the range, maximum, minimum, target and none. To investigate the relation between the chosen factors and responses an overlay plot was constructed.

Evaluation parameter

Physical appearance

The appearances of formulations were observed by visual observation. The observed appearances of the prepared systems were tested on color, clarity [18].

Determination of pH

The pH of the formulated *in-situ* gel was measured using a calibrated pH meter. The pH of the formulated *in-situ* gel was measured by placing the electrode on the surface of the formulation by maintaining the temperature at 25 °C [18].

Syringe ability

All the formulated *in-situ* gels were loaded into a 1 ml syringe with a 20 gauge needle to a constant volume of 1 ml. Formulations that easily pass through the syringe were labelled as pass and hard to pass are labelled as fail [17].

Drug content

Prepared *in-situ* gels were evaluated for drug content by taking 1ml of formulation in a 100 ml volumetric flask. Further, 6.8 pH phosphate buffer was added followed by vigorous shaking and then filtered. Absorbance values were measured with suitable dilutions at λ_{max} 270nm by UV spectrophotometer. Concentrations of the drug were calculated from the standard calibration curve prepared in methanol as stated by to get the drug content [18].

Gelation temperature

2 ml of the formulated *in-situ* gel was instilled in to test tubes that are sealed with paraffin and immersed in a water bath maintained at a temperature of 4°C. The temperature of the water bath was increased with an increment of 1°C. Further, the samples were examined for gelation and the temperature was recorded when would no longer move upon tilting at 90° [18].

Gelling time

Formulated *in-situ* gels were examined for the time taken to form a gel. The test tube inversion method was used to measure the gelling time. A typical procedure involves positioning 2ml of formulated *in-situ* gel in a 10 ml glass tube and placed in a water bath maintained at 37±2 °C and time taken to form gel was noted [19].

In-vitro gelling capacity visual method

To evaluate the formulations for its *in vitro* gelling capacity by the visual method, the colored solution of the gel was prepared. A typical procedure involves placing 2 ml of 6.8 pH phosphate buffer in a 15 ml borosilicate glass test tube and maintained at 37±1°C temperature. Further, 1 ml of colored formulation solution was added to the test tube with the help of a pipette. The formulation was transferred in such a way that pipette was placed at the surface of the fluid in the test tube and formulation was slowly released from the pipette. As the colored formulation comes into contact with simulated saliva, it was immediately converted into a stiff gel-like structure. The gelling capacity of the gel was evaluated based on stiffness and time for which the formed gel remains as such. The color was added to give a visual appearance to the formed gel. The *in vitro* gelling capacity was graded in three categories based on gelation time and time for which the formed gel remains intact [20].

- (+), gels after few minutes, dispersed rapidly.
- (++) , gelation immediate, remains for a few hours.
- (+++) , gelation immediate, remains for an extended period.

***In vitro* gelling capacity by viscosity measurement**

Viscosities of formulations before and after gelation were measured using Brookfield DV-E viscometer using Spindle number-3 at 100 rpm shear rate. In the case of carbopol 934P based systems, the viscosity was recorded at an increasing temperature in the range of 20-30°C and the results were noted [20].

***In vitro* drug release studies**

In vitro drug release study was performed using a Franz diffusion cell consisting of two glass compartments, a sampling port, a Teflon coated magnetic stirrer bead, and a synthetic cellulose membrane (0.45 µm). Simulated saliva having pH 6.8 was used as a dissolution medium. The diffusion cell was water-jacketed, and the temperature was maintained at 37±1°C by continuous circulation of water, in a water bath with a mini-submersible pump. The Franz diffusion cell was placed on a magnetic stirrer, and the stirring rate was maintained at ~250-300 rpm. After equilibration of the dissolution medium at 37±1°C, 1 ml of sample was placed on synthetic cellulose membrane in the donor compartment of the cell with the help of a syringe. Before placing the formulation to the membrane ~2 ml of dissolution medium was placed on the membrane, and the whole assembly was allowed to equilibrate at 37±1°C. At predetermined time intervals, 1 ml

samples of the receptor fluid were taken. The medium was replaced after each sampling. Ciprofloxacin HCl concentration in each sample was determined by diluting 1 ml of the sample up to 100 ml and analyzed spectrophotometrically at 270 nm using a UV-visible spectrophotometer by Shimadzu, Japan [20].

Anti-bacterial activity

The antimicrobial efficiency and prolonged effect of selected controlled release ciprofloxacin HCL *in situ* gel were determined on *S. aureus* and *E. coli* strains as a function of time. The inhibitory effect of formulation on the studied microorganisms was evaluated using agar well diffusion test. Wells were punched into the nutrient agar previously seeded with test organisms and wells were filled with 100 µl of the samples. After allowing diffusion of solution for two-hour the plates were incubated for 24 hrs at 37°C, and the diameters of inhibition zones were measured. The inhibitory effect of optimized gel formulation was compared with a reference standard (pure drug) [21].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Compatibility studies

a. FT-IR analysis

FT-IR spectras of pure CH, polymer mixture and physical mixture were obtained and presented in Table 2 and Figure 1. The peaks of corresponding functional groups of pure CH and polymer mixture were in correlation with the peaks observed in physical mixture. From the results it was evident that no chemical interactions were observed between pure CH and its physical mixture. Therefore, it can be inferred that the selected CH was compatible with the selected polymers.

Table 2: FT-IR spectral data of CH and physical mixture (Drug + Polymers)

Functional Groups	Frequency of pure drug (cm ⁻¹)	Frequency of Physical mixture (cm ⁻¹)
O-H	3129.63	3129.59
C=O Stretch	1697.00	1697.69
-C=O	1627.32	1627.35
C-H	1496.50	1496.51
Aromatic C=C	1381.13	1381.12

Figure 1: FTIR spectras of A. Pure CH, B. Polymer mixture and C. Physical mixture

Preparation of CH loaded *in-situ* gel

The CH *in-situ* gel consisting of badam gum and carbopol 934P were formulated. The as prepared, CH *in-situ* gel formulation existed as pale-yellow colour dispersions.

Central composite design (Table 3 and 4) was employed towards formulating *in situ* gels at 2 factors and 2 levels, with X1 (Carbopol) and X2 (Badam gum) as independent variables, while levels -1 and +1 were chosen as low and high, whereas 0 was chosen as center point.

Table 3: Variables in central composite design of CH *in-situ* gel.

Independent factors		Design level	
Uncoded	Coded	Uncoded	Coded
Carbopol (%)	X ₁	0.5	-1
		0.75	0 (Center point)
		1	1
Badam gum (%)	X ₂	15	-1
		22.5	0 (Center point)
		30	1

Table 4: Observed responses in central composite design of CH *in-situ* gel

Formulation Code	Carbopol (% w/v)	Badam gum (% w/v)	Gelling temperature (°C)	Gelling time (sec)	Time required to release 90% (hrs)
CH1	0.5	15	44	174	5.6
CH 2	0.396447	22.5	42	166	6.2
CH 3	0.5	30	41	149	6.5
CH 4	0.75	11.8934	42	135	7.5
CH 5	0.75	22.5	37	122	8.1
CH 6	0.75	22.5	37	122	8.1
CH 7	0.75	22.5	37	122	8.1
CH 8	0.75	22.5	37	122	8.1
CH 9	0.75	22.5	37	122	8.1
CH 10	0.75	33.1066	38	102	8.5
CH 11	1	15	38	86	8.9
CH 12	1.10355	22.5	37	69	10.1
CH 13	1	30	36	49	10.9

Response analysis for optimization of CH *in-situ* gel

1. Effect of dependent variables on gelling temperature and gelling time

Independent variables (under investigation) effect over gelling temperature and gelling time (as established by central composite design) is presented in Table 4. As can be seen, both carbopol and badam gum displayed a monotonous dependence on gelling temperature and gelling time (Figure 2). Therefore, the combination of carbopol and badam gum showed concentration dependent decrease in gelation temperature. Highest gelation temperature was observed in batch CH1 which had least concentration of polymers and lowest gelation temperature was observed in batch CH13 which had highest concentration of polymers. Batches CH9, CH10 and CH11 showed the ability to form *in-situ* gel nearly at physiological temperature. So, these batches were most desirable for intrapocket-periodontal drug delivery.

Gelling temperature (R1) = 50.1657 -9.03553 Carbopol-0.1540440 Badam gum

Gelling time (R2) = 281.154 -162.589 Carbopol-1.811 Badam gum

2. Effect of dependent variables on time required to release 90% of CH

The release of the drug decreased significantly as the concentration of polymers increased. This indicates that the structure of gel functioned as a resistant barrier to the rate of drug release as the concentration of polymers (carbopol and badam gum) increased. CH1 batch contains lowest amount of carbopol and badam gum therefore it showed 90% drug release in 5.6 hrs. CH13 batch contains highest amount of carbopol and badam gum and therefore it showed drug release up to 10.9 hrs. Therefore, from the results, it can also be concluded that the burst release effect decreases as the concentration of badam gum increases. From the results, it can be clearly concluded that the drug release was affected by the concentration of badam gum that was present in the formulation. This is due to their ability to alter or squeeze the extra micelle aqueous channels of carbopol micelle through which the drug diffuses thereby, delaying the release process.

Time required to release 90% of drug (R3) = 1.4802+6.6077 Carbopol+0.07190 Badam gum

Figure 2: Three-dimensional and contour plots depicting the impact of independent variables on dependent variables

Optimized formulation

The CCD design was useful to analyse the obtained polynomial model, which was used to optimize the process of formulating *in situ* gels with less formulations. Further, overlay plot was used to optimize the designed formulations. Optimized formulation was obtained by setting the constraints. Concentrations recommended by DoE in order to achieve the above mentioned goals were depicted

in the form of an overlay plot (Figure 3) with a desirability which is nearer to 1. The obtained overlay plot highlights the area where there is a chance to obtain the desired responses. The obtained optimized formulation was depicted in the overlay plot as a form of flag. Concentrations of the selected variables in the obtained optimized formulation were 0.79 % of A and 29.99% of B (Table 5)

Figure 3: Overlay plot of optimized CH *in-situ* gel

Table 5: Central composite design enabled CH *in-situ* gel (optimized formulation) obtained via independent variables and their effects on dependent responses.

Value	Carbopol (%)	Badam gum (%)	Gelling temperature (°C)	Gelling time (sec)	Time required to release 90% (hrs)	Desirability
Predicted	0.79	29.99	38.32	96.87	8.91	0.905
Actual	0.8	30	39	97	9	
% Error	0.1	0.01	0.68	0.13	0.9	

Evaluation of CH *in-situ* gel**Physical appearance**

The prepared CH *in-situ* gel was found to be transparent, clear and the colour of formulation was found to be yellow.

pH of formulation

pH of all the formulations was within the range of 6.9-7.4. Further, obtained results suggested that there is no requirement for adjusting the pH using alkylating agents.

Syringeability

All the formulation was found to be easily injectable through 21-gauge needle at 25°C

temperature. This facilitate to injection of sol directly into the periodontal pocket.

Drug content

The drug content of the formulations was found to be in the range of 98.2% - 99.54%. Further, from the results it can be suggested that the loaded CH was uniformly distributed throughout the formulation.

***In-vitro* gelling capacity visual method**

In-vitro gelling capacity of all the formulations was depicted in Table 6. Further, the results suggested that all the formulation batches have formed stiff gels immediately and remained intact for an extended period of time.

Table 6: *In-vitro* gelation study

Formulation code	Degree of gelation
CH1	+++
CH2	+++
CH3	+++
CH4	+++
CH5	+++
CH6	+++
CH7	+++
CH8	+++
CH9	+++
CH10	+++
CH11	+++
CH12	+++
CH13	+++

***In vitro* gelling capacity by viscosity measurement**

The apparent viscosity values were measured for liquid formulations and gel using Brookfield viscometer DV-E with spindle no. 3 at 100 rpm. The selected formulations were poured into the sample adaptor of the viscometer and viscosity was measured. The measurements were carried out using spindle no. 3 at the speed of 50-100 rpm in the sample and the viscosity was measured at 10 min after the rotation of the spindle. The viscosity measurements were made in triplicate using fresh samples each time as shown in Table 7. The marked increase in viscosity of the liquid (sol) formulations was increased from 1671.0 to 1798.0 cps as the concentrations of carbopol and badam gum were increased. It was also seen that the viscosity of the gel formulation was increased from 33313 to 39920 cps as the temperature and ions come in contact of the formulation. Thus, increase in the concentration of the polymers leads to the increase in the viscosity of the formulation.

Table 7: Viscosity profile of solution at 25 °C and gel at 37 °C

Formulation code	In water (at 25 °C)	In pH 6.8 buffer (37 °C)
CH1	1671±3.3	33313±2.5
CH2	1688±2.94	34261±2.7
CH3	1690±3.6	35114±2.1
CH4	1698±3.2	35974±4.9
CH5	1728±5.5	36249±4.5
CH6	1728±5.5	36249±4.5
CH7	1728±5.5	36249±4.5
CH8	1728±5.5	36249±4.5
CH9	1728±5.5	36249±4.5
CH10	1751±2.1	36948±3.6
CH11	1769±2.9	37456±3.1
CH12	1781±3.9	38331±3.2
CH13	1798±4.1	39920±4.5

*mean ± SD, n = 3

***In vitro* drug release studies**

The *in vitro* drug release profiles of the optimized CH *in-situ* gel was done using vertical Franz's diffusion cell (capacity: 14 ml) with synthetic dialysis membrane. Phosphate buffer pH 6.8 was used as a diffusion media. The results showed that the formed gels had the ability to extend the release of drug for the duration of about 9 hours as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: *In vitro* drug release of optimized batch

Anti-bacterial activity

The antibacterial study was carried out against the *E. coli* and *S. aureus* which is gram negative bacteria using test and standard formulation. The test sample and standard sample shows 52mm and 45 mm for *E. coli* and 78 mm and 58 mm for *S. aureus* zone of inhibition, respectively. The inhibition rates to *E. coli* and *S. aureus* of the test and standard material after 24 hrs is shown in Figure 5 and 6. These results can be attributed to the ability of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride *in situ* gel which inhibits the DNA gyrase of bacteria indicating that formulated *in situ* gel have better antibacterial activity as compared to a standard (pure drug).

Figure 5: Anti-bacterial activity (a) *Escherichia coli* (b) *Staphylococcus aureus*

Figure 6: Growth of bacteria in formulation Staphylococcus aureus without drug

CONCLUSION:

The desired CH loaded *in situ* gels were developed using central composite statistical design, which furnished the most favourable concentrations of the carbopol 934P and badam gum to obtain optimal responses (formation of a stiff gel at body temperature rapidly and release 90% of drug by an extended period of 9 hours). The current study demonstrated extended release of loaded CH which may maximize the therapeutic index and reduce dosing frequency. Furthermore, formation of stiff gel for extended period of time when instilled in the periodontal pocket supports the favourable effect of the formulated *in situ* gel to treat periodontitis. The study also supports that the optimized CH loaded *in situ* gel has the ability to inhibit the DNA gyrase of bacteria indicating that formulated *in situ* gel have better antibacterial activity as compared to pure CH. To sum up, the current findings support that CH loaded *in situ* gel could be a promising alternative approach towards treating periodontitis.

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Conflict of Interest

The author confirms that this article content has no conflict of interest.

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